

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

A PEACEFUL GLOBAL EMPIRE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS

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Abstract

The article discusses the positive and negative outcomes of world empires. It determines the prerequisites and characteristics of the genesis of the peaceful global empire of digital platforms that emerged in the 21st century.

Keywords: platform, digital technologies, global empire, netocracy, algorithm.

The 21st century began with global changes in the development of humanity. Digital platforms that shape the future digital world are actively involved in almost all spheres of activity.

The transition of people's activities and daily lives to a digital format is a consistent process in society's development, as well as an objective and reversible challenge to society's progress that cannot be halted.

As time progressed, world empires were established, each experiencing its own ebbs and flows, which are natural according to R. Vernon's universal "Life Cycle Theory": everything that has a beginning has an end.

Previously, the emergence of each new empire was immediately followed by the collapse or disappearance of the old one, or another empire existed in a different territorial space at the same time.

In general, there are conflicting opinions about world empires. On the one hand, the great empires contributed to the civilization of local populations: they advanced science and economics, introduced technological innovations, and disseminated innovative ideas, religion, culture, law, new labor measures, and tools. They also organized residential and communication infrastructure, among other developments.

On the other hand, they perpetrated unprecedented violence, robbery, and genocide against forcibly conquered people.

Since ancient times, the primary objective of all empires has been singular – to employ "brute force", conquering others and seizing their material possessions. This belief persisted throughout the long pre-industrial period, where the prevailing opinion held that wealth could only be attained by appropriating others' property and at the expense of impoverishment.

Over the centuries, scientific progress was slow, and economic growth was minimal. Less attention was given to the development of science, as there was a prevailing belief that production was relatively stable, and efforts to increase it were not a priority.

In 1776, the seminal work of classical economics by the Scottish economist and philosopher Adam Smith, "An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations", was published. This work served as an economic manifesto and laid the foundation for the development of economic science. Among many innovations, a revolutionary idea was articulated for the first time – both the individual and society as a whole

could be enriched by creating and exploiting new opportunities.

The concept of "capital", associated with the concept of "wealth", emerged as a source of additional income. While all capital is considered wealth, not all wealth, such as gold buried in the ground, qualifies as capital because it lacks utility [3].

It was widely recognized that the profitability of capital is determined by progressive ideas that mature in the human mind. This is why the empires of the industrial age prioritized enlightenment, elevating the level of human intelligence, and engaging in research and conquest expeditions that significantly augmented their incomes, production volume, and established the global capital market.

The world empires of the industrial era, influenced by protests from conquered peoples, peacefully ceased to exist in the 20th century.

In the second half of the 20th century, an information crisis emerged: on one hand, the content and volume of accumulated information, and on the other hand, the methods of its effective processing and transmission, came into conflict with each other. It was believed that overcoming the crisis would be possible only through the adoption of new information processing technologies.

This is how the demand for the Internet and related information and communication technologies, digital platforms, and social networks (Google, Yahoo, Apple, Microsoft, and Facebook) arose. Information, as an intangible asset, has become the fundamental resource for the development of society.

The question naturally arises: who creates and owns the information?

Information is intensively created, collected, and distributed by people on global search systems and social network platforms.

The Internet gave birth to giant transnational companies in the IT field and a new ruling class of their owners – netocrats.

They were the first to understand the difference between information and knowledge, especially the value of exclusive knowledge, making them the dominant class in the new society [1].

Netocrats were the first to appear "at the right time, in the right place". They "have been able to adapt to changes better than others" (Ch. Darwin) and have found great benefits in the global "data value chain".

They mostly own not real estate but intangible capital (e.g., software, operating systems...) and equipment (e.g., servers). For netocrats, buildings and streamline are "excessive burdens". Their task is simple: to obtain from all possible sources the valuable resource of modern times – the personal information of consumers, to process it, to transform it into a knowledge-containing product, and to sell it. Therefore, to gain power, all efforts were shifted to the creation and effective use of digital technologies, thus providing easy access to information and levers to influence others.

Today, they fully control over the "global information mine", tapping into its inexhaustible resource of "raw" information. Although this information is freely available to everyone, the netocrats own the filtering technologies (algorithms) and exclusive knowledge, treating them as valuable commodities and specific forms of intelligence – assets only they possess.

Simultaneously, the volume of the "global information deposit" is not decreasing; on the contrary, it is growing intensively. Essentially, the netocrats are continually enriched by new "raw" informational mass without any additional effort on their part.

As a result, an unprecedented model of world hegemony is emerging – a new form of governance in the shape of a peaceful global empire of digital platforms. This empire, facilitated by digital technologies, is gradually taking form alongside enhancements in people's well-being, orchestrated by its owners, leading to an unprecedented increase in financial capital.

In contrast to traditional empires throughout human development, the peaceful global empire of digital platforms:

1. Develops and expands not through the coarse method of influencing others, not by "muscle power", but by "soft power" – attractiveness. This method achieves compliance within its information base, involving the intensive and continuous (24/7/365) engagement of the "conquered" people.

2. Is grounded not in combat strategies and tactics but in the perfection and development of digital technologies.

3. It is not ruled by one single country or one ethno-cultural group, but in intense competition, on different continents (mainly, North America and Eurasia) founded by a small group of private IT company owners – netocrats.

4. "Voluntarily conquered" people do not show hidden aggression or obvious aggression towards him, but eagerness and interest.

5. It represents the first peaceful empire in the history of mankind that does not physically exploit its "conquered" people. Regardless of their economic status, social standing, nationality, gender, or any other characteristic, it encourages the emergence and utilization of new opportunities for development and enrichment. From this perspective, its operation aligns perfectly with the wisdom of A. In accordance with the concept articulated by Smith three and a half centuries ago – both as an individual economic actor and within the potential for the development and enrichment of society as a whole.

6. It exists simultaneously and ubiquitously, functioning virtually, somewhere in the "clouds", devoid of weapons and heavy combat equipment. Established geographical boundaries and adjacent territories systematically expand its sphere of activity, positioning it as a prospective world empire with significant development prospects in the future.

7. At its initial stage of development, it generates substantial income by utilizing rapidly growing and systematically updated data that reflects the economic behavior of others. This data serves as a specific "raw" material, transformed into a new intangible asset – valuable information that, for the purpose of advertising innovative products/services, is sold at a relatively high price [4].

8. It consumes non-limited natural resources but continually accumulates growing intangible resources [2].

The characteristic features of the global empire of digital platforms are evident from the above; however, it is equally important to note that it cannot be conquered, destroyed, or dismantled by the forceful methods known to mankind. In the history of societal development, such as through the exertion of fighting force by conquered peoples, their physical destruction by others, and/or the seizure of wealth, the empire remains resilient.

The global empire of digital platforms cannot be acquired through force; its strength lies in systematic development and expansion. It is not land or material possessions that make it formidable, but an ever-increasing and renewable intangible asset – innovative technologies that transform user data into knowledge-rich information. In the form of skills, these technologies are embedded in the minds and information base of the empire's owners. For example, the wealth and reputation of the state of California are determined not by its historical gold deposits but by Silicon Valley – a globally significant high-tech industrial zone encompassing computer and electronic industries, serving as a robust hub for the production of cutting-edge products.

Now, consider the hypothetical scenario: What if the state of California were attacked using the "law of the jungle" or "brute force"? What wealth would it gain in return?

The answer lies beyond the realm of rich deposits of silicon in Silicon Valley. Instead, it resides in the collective expertise of the world's elite digital platforms (Google, Yahoo, Apple, Microsoft, Facebook, Amazon, Intel, etc.), whose wealth is vested in the minds of software development engineers. Rather than extracting resources, they amass billions of dollars through trade and economic collaboration with these technological giants, primarily by selling their computer programs.

Based on the aforementioned, the peaceful global empire of digital platforms will continue to function, as its weakening and destruction will only become possible with the emergence of new innovative solutions that are more attractive.

Conclusions:

1. A completely new process of innovative development for humanity is underway – the digital revolution. This revolution serves as a universal challenge – an objective, extremely complex, and irreversible event with both positive and negative outcomes, fundamentally altering all spheres of public activity and people's lives.

2. The new corporate ruling class, known as netocrats, is gaining strength. These netocrats exercise complete control over the valuable information world "minefield", reflecting the economic behavior of consumers and experiencing systematic growth. They obtain colossal profits by selling updated data and participating in the "global data value chain" that proves beneficial for them. Consequently, a peaceful global empire of extraordinary and previously unheard-of digital platforms, an economic system led by netocrats, has been established – a modern "corporation" or what can be termed as a "Corporate Digital Dictatorship". This system is managed by a global giant consisting of pri-

vate transnational IT companies in conditions of intense competition, all led by a small group of individuals.

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